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Summative Assessment of Literacy and Numeracy

A Review of the Literature

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The views expressed in this report are those of the author, and not his institution.

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Summary

Because of a dearth of systematic reviews based in the international literature on summative assessment (i.e., outcomes of experimental studies on the effects of different approaches to summative assessment), this review primarily focuses on current international trends with regard to large-scale assessments implemented at national and state levels. It does not include a detailed consideration of state examinations or international assessments, though such assessments are referred to.

Summative assessment can be defined as ‘the assessment of students that occurs at the end of a period of instruction. [It] provides a holistic measurement of an individual’s knowledge, skills and dispositions. . .’ (Nicholas, 2018, p. 1634). In the context of the current L&N strategy, it relates to assessments such as the National Assessments of English Reading and Mathematics (NAREM) and the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA), both of which are used to set national targets for student performance in literacy and numeracy and are essentially low-stakes assessments for most stakeholders. It also encompasses the standardised tests that are currently administered to pupils in the Second, Fourth and Sixth classes in primary schools, which can be viewed as high-stakes, though certainly not to the same extent as census-based national or state-level assessments in Australia, England and the US, where summative assessment data may also be used for such purposes as evaluating the effectiveness of schools and teachers in promoting student achievement.

A tension can arise between the purposes of formative or classroom-based assessment, on the one hand, and summative assessment on the other, with trade-offs in design needed between the fine-grained information required by teachers during a particular lesson or unit of study (formative) and the broad and more comprehensive summary information needed by policy makers (summative) (see Shepherd et al., 2018). Summative assessment often enjoys a higher status than formative assessment, and this gives rise to the possibility that teaching and learning will focus more on preparing students for summative assessment, with less attention or recognition given to formative assessment. O’Leary et al. (2019) have argued that summative assessments should provide more formative information, especially for at-risk groups such as disadvantaged students, students for whom English is an additional language, and students with special educational needs. In the future, it is likely that formative and summative assessment will merge to a greater extent, particularly as technology facilitates the scoring of more complex assessment tasks (Klenkowski & Wyatt-Smith, 2012). Looney

(2019) has noted that electronic scoring systems can now score complex cognitive tasks such as problem solving, open-ended performances such as written essays, and student collaboration on constructed response formats, enabling the use of more complex tasks in summative assessment.

Recent developments in technology have facilitated the use of interim summative assessments to generate formative assessment information. For example, interim assessment blocks (IABs) can be used throughout the school year to assess smaller bundles of content, with focused IABs assessing a limited number of learning outcomes (e.g., multiplication and division within 100, numbers and operations in base 10). In some cases, performance may be reported on the same scales as full standardised tests. In New Zealand's e-assTTle programme (Carneige-Harding, 2016), teachers can play a role in the selection of items for interim tests that are either 12 or 60 minutes in length. Schildkamp and Kuiper (2010) and Poortman and Schildkamp (2016) have provided evidence that Data-based Decision Making (DBDM), which involves the systematic analysis of existing data sources (such as interim assessments) within the school by teachers, can promote learning, whether at the level of the school, the class or the individual student.

Technology has also facilitated other developments in summative assessment. Bennett (2015) noted a range of possibilities including adaptive testing (allowing greater precision in identifying where the performance of high- and low-achieving students lies), the assessment of new constructs, the development of new item-types, automated scoring, and the administration of tests at different times during the school year with performance aggregated to determine proficiency (that is, greater integration of instruction and assessment). Some of these developments are already evident in international assessments such as PISA, which now incorporates adaptive testing, and may soon be reflected in nationally-developed tests.

Technology may also help to make current summative assessments more inclusive of all students in the education system including those with special education needs by providing a range of accommodations such as large print and assistive technology.

National Curriculum Assessment in England (which is still paper-based) includes alternative teacher-based assessments for students who are studying well below the curriculum for their class level, and an Engagement Model for the most-challenged students, where teachers rate them on constructs such as persistence and initiation (see Standards and Testing Agency, 2021).

In recent years, national and state-level assessment programmes in other countries have begun to report measures of student progress, alongside scores that reflect performance at a

particular point in time. The Massachusetts Comprehensive Assessment System (MCAS) reports on performance with reference to student growth percentiles (e.g., Lockwood & Cestellano, 2015). These enable stakeholders to evaluate growth in performance relative to an intake measure such as performance on an earlier assessment. National Curriculum Assessment in England at Key Stage 2 has used a similar approach, allowing for a comparison between a student's expected score (based on how students with similar scores at Key Stage 1 perform at Key Stage 2) and their achieved score. Although student scores derived from these and other valued added models are often used to evaluate teacher and school effectiveness (a practice not without problems – see Marks, 2021; Guarino, 2018), they may be of value in monitoring the progress of individual students and groups.

A number of national assessment programmes also support the interpretation of test scores by taking socio-economic context into account. The Australian National Assessment Programme – Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN), which is administered on an annual basis in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9, reports average performance at school level with reference to the performance of other students with similar socioeconomic backgrounds. The focus on students (rather than schools) is intended to reduce competition between schools. In Scotland, schools at upper-secondary level can compare the performance of their school leavers on literacy and numeracy (based on national exams) against virtual comparators (groups of students of similar socioeconomic background). Although not without criticism, these approaches allow for an additional layer of interpretation in reviewing performance.

The reporting of test scores (for example, STen scores) to parents and other stakeholders is not uncommon in assessment programmes in other countries. However, these are often accompanied by descriptors of performance. In England, parents and other stakeholders are informed if students have reached the expected performance level for their age group, essentially based on a single cut-off score. In Massachusetts, performance is also reported with respect to **level such** as 'partially meeting expectations', 'meeting expectations' and 'exceeding expectations'. These descriptors can provide stakeholders with more specific, standards- or curriculum-based based feedback on performance.

In assessing literacy and numeracy, a number of assessment programmes (most noticeably PISA) seek to include authentic, real-life assessment tasks. Such tasks seem to capture the essence of literacy and numeracy (as opposed to English reading and mathematics), as they seek to measure performance on the types of tasks that students would be expected to encounter outside of school, as well as in school contexts. The transition of PISA to computer has also seen a shift from more basic reading literacy to digital literacy,

where a broader range of assessment tasks based on multiple texts and a greater emphasis on evaluating information, are presented. Countries such as Australia, England and the United States all include the assessment of writing – a key component of literacy – in their assessment programmes, while it is noticeably absent in Ireland. Finally, assessment programmes such as NAPLAN in Australia and PISA have begun to implement online measures of interactive or collaborative problem solving on a trial basis. This reflects an interest in capturing another real-life skill – the ability of students to interact with others in solving real-life problems.

It is noteworthy that a key recommendation relating to assessment in the initial NLNS report has not been implemented. This relates to the administration of standardised measures of literacy and numeracy to post-primary students at the end of Second year. The intention was that these tests would provide useful information to schools about students' progress and their learning needs. They would also contribute information on standards at national level, and would provide a useful reference point if PISA scores changed as they did in 2009. Although the implementation of standardised testing at the end of Second year was postponed to enable schools to implement new specifications and assessment approaches at Junior Cycle level, the case for implementing them has not changed. Also, as envisaged in the interim review of the NLNS, there would be value in assessing pupils' digital literacy skills in schools selected to take part in NAERM to heighten teachers' awareness of the importance of promoting such skills.

Recommendations – (Improving Assessment and Evaluation Pillar)

1. Consideration should be given to implementing standardised tests of literacy and numeracy at post-primary level in English- and Irish-medium school, as envisaged in the 2011 National Literacy and Numeracy Strategy. The requisite tests have already been developed and are available online, and schools should be supported in implementing them, and in interpreting the outcomes to inform planning at school and individual student levels.
2. The National Assessments of English Reading and Mathematics at primary level should be expanded to include an assessment of digital literacy at Sixth class, as

envisaged in the 2017 Interim NLNS Review. Assessments of online and paper-based writing should be administered in a subsample of schools.

3. Any modifications to the current system of implementing and reporting on the outcomes of standardised tests in Second, Fourth and Sixth classes in primary schools, should be handled carefully so that such tests do not place additional constraints on teaching and learning, or on the wellbeing of stakeholders (see O’Leary et al., 2019). However, practices in other countries around the reporting of individual and group progress over time (for example, use of student growth percentiles) should be considered. There would also be value in contextualising aggregated student performance, by, for example, using virtual comparators (pseudo schools with similar socioeconomic characteristics). These approaches could help to ensure that schools and teachers can access better performance data to support data-based decision making.
4. The development of short, online interim assessments across a range of areas in literacy and numeracy should be considered, beginning with primary level. These assessments, comprising short tests in specific areas (e.g., informational texts in reading, fractions in mathematics) would be used by teachers on a needs basis throughout the school year, to support them in targeting instruction in literacy and numeracy.
5. The practice in Ireland of allowing the use of multiple tests and aggregating outcomes across tests at national level is unusual by international standards. The administration of a single secure, regularly-updated test across all schools is preferable and this can be facilitated by technology.
6. The affordances of technology to facilitate adaptive testing, where students are provided with sets of test items based on their own ability, should be considered where computer-based testing is available, as this is likely to make testing a more positive experience for students (including some with special education needs) and provide greater clarity on the performance of high- and low-achieving students.

7. Consideration should be given to reporting descriptors of achievement, alongside test scores in testing programmes. These are similar to the proficiency levels in NAERM. Descriptors such as ‘working towards expectations’, ‘partially meeting expectations’, ‘meeting expectations’ and ‘exceeding expectations’ may be useful to stakeholders, in terms of understanding the needs of students relative to expectations for their class level, and allocating instructional support.
8. In line with recommendations in earlier Irish studies (e.g., Douglas et al., 2012), efforts should be made to make large-scale assessments such as the National Assessment of English Reading and Mathematics (NAERM) more inclusive, so that all students, including those with special education needs, can participate. Accommodations can include additional time, adaptations to tests, prompts, accessibility objects in mathematics, and aural input. The expansion of computer-based testing should facilitate some of these.
9. Alternative approaches to assessment should be made available to cater for students who are currently exempted from taking standardised tests at the end of the Second, Fourth and Sixth classes. These might include alternative assessments of literacy and numeracy, teacher-based assessments, and, where such assessments are not relevant, assessments of underlying learning skills such as communication, initiation and persistence. Outcomes should be reported to the DE alongside regular results, so that a record of the literacy and numeracy skills of all students in a school is available in aggregated form.

Introduction

Unlike other reports in this series, this report on summative assessment is not based on published systematic reviews of the literature as such reviews are not readily available in the context of describing the impact of many summative assessments. Rather, this report aims to describe current international trends and issues in summative assessment. The following questions are addressed:

1. What is summative assessment?
2. Can formative and summative assessment be linked?
3. What is the value of interim and ongoing assessment using summative tools?
4. What are the implications of computer-based delivery for summative assessment?
5. How can summative assessments be adapted for students with learning difficulties?
6. What are some recent developments in reporting on national large-scale summative assessments?
7. How can 21st century skills related to literacy and numeracy be assessed in large-scale summative assessments?

Q1: What is Summative Assessment?

According to Nicholas (2018), summative assessment is:

. . .the assessment of students that occurs at the end of a period of instruction. The purpose of summative assessment is to provide teachers and others with a summary view of learning and accomplishments.[It] provides a holistic measurement of an individual's knowledge, skills, or dispositions Summative assessment consists of a variety of different formats from multiple-choice exams to research papers to portfolios of student work. (p. 1634-1635)

Summative assessment has also become synonymous with large-scale testing programs such as the NAEP (National Assessment of Educational Progress) in the United States, the Key Stage SATs (Standard Attainment Tests) in the UK, and NAPLAN (National Assessment Program – Literacy and Numeracy) in Australia. Like the National Assessments of English Reading and Mathematics in Ireland, these assessments are used by policy makers to monitor the educational system's progress and ensure that national standards are maintained. In the same vein, international assessments such as the Programme for International Study Assessment (PISA), the Trends in International Mathematics and Science Study (TIMSS), and the Progress in International Reading Literacy Study (PIRLS) are large-scale international summative assessments that are primarily designed to provide policy

makers with data on student achievement.

Summative assessment can be contrasted with formative assessment, which tends to be classroom-based, with a focus on providing students with (or enabling students to generate) feedback, that can then be used to improve learning. In their comparison of formative and summative assessment, Shepherd et al. (2018) noted the trade-offs in assessment design are needed between the fine-grained information required by teachers during a particular lesson or unit of study (formative), and the broad and more comprehensive summary information needed by policy makers on a much less frequent basis (e.g., annually or less often) (summative). Table 1 illustrates key features of formative and summative assessment.

Table 1: Features of formative and summative assessment*

Formative Classroom-based Assessment	Summative Assessment
Administration procedures vary	Standardised administrative procedures
Administered at unique times	Uniform administration dates
Can involve assisted performance (e.g., as in dynamic assessment)	Independent performance by students (though students with learning difficulties may be offered accommodations)
Local curriculum	Amalgam of curricula

*Based on Shepherd et al. (2018).

Notwithstanding the criticisms around many summative testing programmes, Bennett (2011) has pointed to some formative benefits of summative assessment, which seem to relate more to standardised tests and examinations than to international and national assessments, which students typically do not prepare for in advance:

- If the content, format and design of the test offer a sufficiently rich domain representation, preparing for the summative test can be a valuable learning experience; it can encourage students to consolidate and organise knowledge, rehearse domain-relevant processes and strategies, and establish greater links to conditions of use and greater automaticity in execution.
- Taking a test can both enhance learning by strengthening the representation of information retrieved during the test and also slow the rate of forgetting.
- Summative assessment may support learning by providing a limited type of formative information by, for example, linking performance to theoretically or empirically based learning progressions.

Summative assessment in Ireland, as it relates to the National Literacy and Numeracy Strategy, can be considered with reference to three broad assessment programmes:

- PISA, because national targets for literacy and numeracy at post-primary level are based on this assessment; furthermore, the domain of mathematical literacy in PISA is reasonably closely aligned to numeracy, as the term is understood in the context of the Strategy;
- The National Assessments of Mathematics and Reading Literacy (NAMER), as targets for literacy and numeracy at primary level are based on these assessments; most recently, targets for DEIS schools based on the National Assessments were incorporated into the Strategy.
- Standardised tests administered by primary schools to pupils at the end of Second, Fourth and Sixth classes, as the Strategy requires schools to report results of these tests to Boards of Management and to the Department (see O’Leary et al., 2019, for a detailed overview of how such tests are used in schools and how teachers perceive their influence on teaching and learning).

Q2: Can Formative and Summative Assessments Be Linked?

A key issue for policy makers and test developers concerns the extent to which formative and summative assessments can be combined. This includes the extent to which coursework or performance assessments completed in students’ classrooms can contribute to national assessments and examinations.

According to Shepherd et al. (2018), there are four layers that should be taken into account in designing an assessment system:

- Formative assessment in classrooms as part of ongoing instruction – assessment occasions may be integrated with instructional activities, and may be unmarked for students as instances of evaluation
- Classroom summative grading practices
- District-level curriculum-based programme evaluation¹
- National-level standards-based assessment and accountability²

These elements can be viewed as varying according to such factors as timing, frequency, immediacy of feedback and need for standardization. A key element is curriculum specificity, on the basis that curriculum materials, embedded assessments, and accompanying professional development are the means by which theories of learning come to be enacted in

¹ In Ireland, programme evaluation occurs in the context of DEIS and other initiatives.

² In Ireland, this includes national assessments and standardised tests at primary level and examinations at post-primary level.

classrooms. Arguably, these can also be made coherent across levels of an educational system. Shepherd et al. argue that models of cognition and learning should provide a basis for designing and implementing theory-driven instructional and assessment practice. A theory or set of beliefs informs the observation methods that are applied during assessments, and interpretative frameworks are then used to draw inferences about students' competencies.

According to Shepherd et al., while assessment at all levels should draw on the same underlying theories of learning, such models can be at a higher level of aggregation when the purpose is to monitor trends, or for programme evaluation, and more fine-grained to guide teaching and learning at classroom level. Figure 1 shows the interaction of these elements, and highlights the role of teacher professional development in leveraging the benefits of different types of assessment.

Shepherd et al. state that applying sociocultural theory allows for the coherent co-design of curriculum, instruction and assessment to enable deep learning over time that is rooted in the practices of specific disciplines. Hence, learning involves explaining phenomena and solving problems using the kinds of practices that disciplinary experts use.

Among others, Looney (2019) argues for the integration of formative (classroom-based) assessments and larger summative assessments (for example, national assessments).

However, she acknowledges some key challenges:

- Creating reliable measures of higher-order skills, such as problem solving and collaboration, can be difficult in the context of large-scale assessments (it is easier to assess such skills in classroom-based assessments)
- Data gathered in large-scale assessments are not at the level of detail needed to diagnose individual student needs for formative purposes.
- The categorisation of student performance using terms such as below basic, basic, proficient and advanced are too broad to provide any kind of diagnostic assessment necessary for profiling individual students' needs.

Nevertheless, Looney notes some recent developments that can be viewed as 'promising', including innovative scoring systems that score student performance electronically on complex cognitive tasks (problem solving), on open-ended performances such as written essays, and on student collaboration on constructed response formats, thereby facilitating the use of more complex tasks in summative assessments.

Figure 1: Learning Theory and Components of Assessment

*Motivations include self-regulation, self-efficacy, sense of belonging and identity. Adapted from Shepherd et al. (2018).

Ultimately, a balance needs to be found between formative and summative assessment. This raises the question as to whether the standardised tests administered to students can also be used for diagnosis and learning improvement. When used for such purposes, testing is the best interests of all students, including those at risk of not making satisfactory progress, and the outcomes of testing are used for student identification, targeted intervention and tracking learning growth over time (for individual students and groups of students) – something Klenkowski and Wyatt-Smith (2012) argue improves both equity and quality. High-stakes testing may work against these activities, as the focus switches to issues such as school- and teacher effectiveness.

The issue of how the results of standardised tests administered to students in Second, Fourth and Sixth classes in primary schools in Ireland on an annual basis might be used more formatively was addressed in a study by O’Leary et al. (2019). They recommended that. . .

Consideration should be given to changing mandated testing from the summer term to the autumn term (or providing schools with this option). Testing in the autumn might alleviate the pressure/anxiety felt by teachers and pupils while increasing the possibility of test data being used for formative purposes throughout the school year. The timing would also make it possible for the results of standardised tests to be communicated and explained at parent/teacher meetings. (page ix)

A recommendation in the report by O’Leary et al. (2019) relating to the use of standardised tests in DEIS schools, and, more generally, relating to their use with students with special education needs, and for whom English is an additional language, also focuses on the formative use of outcomes of standardised tests:

Some system of criterion-referenced in addition to norm-referenced interpretations should be considered for use in DEIS/EAL/SEN contexts. Reporting of individual pupil progress to parents could be done in this way with the percentages of students meeting particular benchmarked standards reported to BOMs and the DES. The system might help to identify and facilitate the measurement of appropriate learning goals, meet the differentiated needs of the pupils, be more reflective of teaching and learning practices in inclusive and disadvantaged settings, and affirm teacher effort and professionalism. (page x).

In discussing how a framework for assessment linked to the revised Primary curriculum in Ireland might be developed, Lysaght et al. (2019) warn against over-prescriptive use of the terms ‘formative’ and ‘summative’ assessment, claiming that ‘the practice of *rigidly classifying* every instance of assessment as being either formative or summative may not be the most useful starting point for informing everyday practice’ (p. 22).

Q3: What is the Value of Interim and Ongoing Assessment Using Summative Tools?

Traditionally, in countries and states with annual standardised testing programmes, tests have been administered at the end of a school year, and the results have been mainly used for summative purposes – providing an overall view of students’ performance. Here, further consideration is given to how the outcomes of standardised tests and other assessments can also be used to generate formative assessment data, and what effect such tests might have on learning outcomes. Interim assessments, which are typically administered during the school year rather than at its conclusion, can include the following:

- Interim Comprehensive Assessments (ICAs), which are designed to assess a broad set of content and provide a high-level overview of student performance in the same way

as summative assessments. The ICAs may also be helpful as a source of information if a student is new to a system and educational records are not available, when prioritising the allocation of additional instructional support, and as a mid-year progress check. According to Dixson and Worrell (2016), interim assessments of this kind can also be viewed as practice for standardised tests administered later in the school year.

- Interim Assessment Blocks (IABs) are assessments teachers can use throughout the school year to assess smaller bundles of content than ICAs. They are intended to provide educators and students with the ability to check student performance at any given moment in time, and educators can use results to determine next steps for instruction. IABs assess between three and eight assessment targets. Since IABs are more granular than the ICAs, educators can use IABs during the school year more consistently and frequently with the sequence of their curricula. There are typically 10 to 18 items on IABs.
- Focused IABs assess no more than three assessment targets to provide educators with a more detailed understanding of student learning. There are typically 10 to 15 items on Focused IABs. For example, Focused IABs are available from Smarter Balanced (a US assessment consortium) for grade 3 mathematics in the following areas:
 - Multiply and divide within 100
 - Linear and area measurement
 - Properties of multiplication and division
 - Number and operations in base 10
 - Number and operations – fractions
 - Time, volume and mass
 - Geometry

Key features of interim assessments (as conceptualised by Smarter Balanced (2021), include:

- Flexible administration (in contrast to ‘official’ summative assessments, which are administered with reference to strict guidelines)
- Interactive administration, where students discuss or work on test items in groups
- Tailor-made tests – using an assessment portal, teachers can select those items that match the taught curriculum

- Performance is reported on the same scales as used in summative assessments, though interim assessments are not designed to be used for accountability purposes
- Can be used to measure students' knowledge and skills in grade levels outside the students' enrolled grades
- Teachers can view test questions and student responses to inform possible next instructional steps with students. This provides a diagnostic or formative dimension to interim assessments.

Hence, interim assessments, though they may be commercially developed, and linked to end-of-year summative assessments, can be quite similar to classroom-based assessments, especially when they are used to set learning targets or establish next steps in learning.

Another approach to interim testing that combines formative and summative assessment using technology is the e-asTTle project in New Zealand.³ This online tool is designed to assess students' progress in reading, mathematics, writing and indigenous languages. The reading and mathematics tests have been developed for students in Years 5-10 (10-15 year olds), while the writing tool has been developed for children in Years 1-10. e-asTTle is intended to provide teachers and school leaders with information that can be used to inform learning programmes, and to apply teaching practice that maximises individual student learning. However, outcomes can also be used for planning purposes, for helping students to understand their progress, and for involving parents in discussion on how well their children are doing. Key features of e-assTTle include:

- The development of tests by teachers, drawing on large item banks, allowing for alignment to preferred (or all) aspects of the curriculum; tests can be either 12 minutes or 60 minutes in duration; the number of strands in a subject area that can be assessed depends on test length, with 5 strands requiring 60 minutes;
- While primarily designed for online assessments, tests can also be delivered on paper;
- Questions follow a multiple-choice format, or are short-answer, with teachers choosing preferred proportions; the teacher can also select the proportion of closed (computer-scored) to open items on a test;
- There is provision for computer-adaptive testing; teachers can choose whether e-asTTle selects the difficulty of the assessment based on information collected as the student completes the assessment (i.e., computer-adaptive testing) and can select the initial difficulty level.

³ See <https://e-asttle.tki.org.nz/>

- Short attitude assessments can be administered in conjunction with the tests;
- Teachers can decide whether multiple-choice questions are marked automatically.
- Teachers can mark open-ended questions online, with access to correct examples;
- Access is given to information on the performance of individual students, classes and schools, compared to the national average and curriculum requirements (including curriculum levels);
- Comparisons to other groups such as gender, ethnicity, English as a second language, and ‘schools like mine’ can be generated;
- Specific feedback on student performance is provided (rather than simply reporting a single score). This feedback can be drawn on in planning teaching and learning;
- Teachers are directed to relevant online resources for raising student achievement more efficiently;

A study by Carneige-Harding (2016) found that teachers of students in Years 7-9 in minority settings who used e-assTTle successfully transitioned to formative assessment and evidence-based teaching practices, though progress of Year 7 students was limited, perhaps reflecting challenges in making the transition from primary to post-primary level.

Webber (2020) found the e-assTTle English-language versions of the reading and mathematics tests to be both valid and reliable, and to produce similar outcomes to PISA for students who took both assessments. However, it was also noted that students taking e-assTTle at primary level tended to be of higher ability than students in general, and that students taking e-assTTle at post-primary tended to be of lower ability.

A number of studies have found positive effects for using test data to improve student learning based on interim or ongoing assessment via Data-based Decision Making (DBDM). According to Schildkamp and Kuiper (2010), DBDM involves ‘systematically analysing existing data sources within the school, applying outcomes of analyses to innovate teaching, curricula, and school performance, and implementing and evaluating these innovations’ (p. 482). Schildkamp and Kuiper (2010) note that DMBD can take place at the level of the school, the classroom and the student. For example, teachers in classrooms may modify instructional strategies based on their analysis of test data. Poortman and Schildkamp (2016) reported that, following an intervention designed to support schools to analyze their data, five of nine schools succeeded in raising achievement.

Schildkamp et al. (2020) also note that data for DBDM can extend beyond test results, to also include homework assignments, curriculum-embedded assessments, and structured

observations from daily classroom practice. They characterise DBDM as a systematic process that begins with a specific purpose such as reducing the gap between current and desired levels of student achievement with:

- Teachers identifying measurable goals for all students in their classrooms
- Teachers collecting data to identify possible causes of achievement gaps
- Determination of actions to be taken based on the data, including changes in instruction
- Collection of new data to evaluate the impact of instructional change.

Q4: What are the Implications of Computer-based Delivery for Summative Assessments?

In recent years, there has been a significant expansion in the use of technology to administer, score and report on the outcomes of summative assessment. For example, PISA is now administered on computer in most participating countries. In PISA 2018, adaptive testing was used in reading literacy for the first time, facilitating a better match between the texts and items students are asked to respond to, and their overall ability as readers, thereby making the assessment a more meaningful experience for students. PISA also used machine scoring to score some constructed response items, though scoring by humans was implemented in cases where a direct match could not be found between a student's response and the database of responses assembled during piloting.

The use of computers in PISA and in other assessment programmes has also led to substantial revisions to test frameworks to accommodate new stimuli and item types. On PISA reading literacy, for example, these relate to new reading tasks involving comprehension of multiple texts including webpages, as well as a stronger emphasis on evaluating the source and credibility of information.

Here in Ireland, the Educational Research Centre now offers most of its primary tests (from Third class upwards) on paper and computer, while all its tests at post-primary level are available on computer only. This means that individual results and class reports can be generated within minutes of students completing their tests. However, the National Assessments of English Reading and Mathematics are not yet offered electronically.

Bennett (2015) provides a useful breakdown of the stages of implementation in computer-based testing. These are useful for evaluating the progress that has been made, and what further steps can be taken.

Table 2: Computer-based Testing – Stages of Implementation

Stage	Description	Nature of Tests	Role of Schools	Role of Test Development Agencies
First-generation computer-based testing	An infrastructure-building activity, laying the foundation for tests to be delivered in a new medium; Tests may be adaptive, allowing greater precision in terms of pinpointing where the performance of high- and low-achieving students lies. The performance of all students (except those with the most serious disabilities) can be placed on the same underlying scale.	First-generation measures closely resemble traditional tests; differ marginally in design and item format from their paper counterparts; are administered as an isolated, “onetime” event; and take limited advantage of technology.	Purchase of infrastructure (tablets, computers, proxy servers); training of staff to deal with set-up, administration and proctoring of online tests, including dealing with technical failure.	Item creation, item banking, test assembly, quality control, and security will require adopting new processes, licensing software, and retraining staff.
Second-generation	In second-generation tests, qualitative (but incremental) change and efficiency improvement become the driving goals; Initial attempts may be made to measure new constructs, beginning to change what is Assessed; Because of its novelty, the use of technology in this generation may sometimes take precedence over substantive consideration.	Second-generation tests use less traditional item formats (e.g., ones involving multimedia stimuli, short constructed response, static performance tasks like essays). Automated scoring may be used.		Use of the Internet for a wide variety of internal processes (item review, standard setting, human online scoring), as well as for interactions with test users.

Table 2: Computer-based Testing – Stages of Implementation (continued)

Stage	Description	Nature of Tests	Role of Schools	Role of Test Development Agencies
Third-generation	<p>The third generation of assessments is one of reinvention occurring on multiple fronts simultaneously; It is in this third generation that what was, at first, an evolution driven primarily by technology becomes driven by substance.</p> <p>Tests may be administered in parts – e.g., after 75% of the school year has elapsed, and after 90%, with performance aggregated across the two tests to determine proficiency.</p>	<p>Assessments serve both institutional and individual-learning purposes. Second, they are designed from cognitive principles and theory-based domain models. Third, the assessments use complex simulations and other interactive performance tasks that replicate important features of real environments, allow more natural interaction with computers, and assess new skills in more sophisticated ways. Finally, the assessments are more integrated with instruction, sampling performance repeatedly over time.</p>		

Source: Bennett (2015)

In the context of defending the Australian National Assessment Programme (NAPLAN), Joseph (2018, p. 12) describes how the transition to computer-based testing can be expected to benefit students and other stakeholders:

- More timely results, with marks returned to schools in weeks rather than in months, enabling schools and teachers to intervene more quickly to help individual students.
- Tailored questioning for students’ abilities, ensuring that students are asked questions appropriate to their own level, and that the tests more accurately assess their literacy and numeracy skills. An Australian study, by Martin and Lazendic (2018), is cited by Joseph as showing that computer-adaptive testing can (a)

yield greater achievement measurement precision; (b) contribute to some positive test-relevant motivation and engagement effects; (c) have more positive effects for older (year 9) students at a developmental stage when they may be less motivated and engaged.

A number of aspects of digital assessment are not covered under Bennett's framework, and these include the use of accessibility features to support the inclusion of students with special education needs, and the reporting of assessment results to different stakeholders (teachers, students, schools etc.). These are considered in the next sections of this paper.

Q5: How Can Summative Assessment be Adapted for Children with Learning Difficulties/Special Education Needs?

Bennett (2015) describes recent trends in the administration of assessments by computer, including the embedding of accessibility features directly into test delivery. These can be categorised as follows:

- *Universal tools* – available to all students – e.g., English glossaries (such as pop-up definitions of selected construct-irrelevant variables), highlighter, spell-check and Zoom.
- *Designated supports* – available to students deemed by their school to require them – e.g., masking, colour contrast, text-to-speech (for all items except reading passages), and glossary translation in multiple languages.
- *Accommodations* – available to students with assessed needs – Sign language video presentation (for listening and mathematics items), text-to-speech, closed-captioning (for listening items).

The second and third categories are especially relevant to addressing the needs of students with learning difficulties and special education needs. They suggest approaches that might be employed to ensure that students who might otherwise be excluded from assessment programmes can be included if the affordances of technology are drawn on.

One of the disadvantages of norm-based summative assessments is that they often exclude a small cohort of learners at the lower end. A circular issued to primary schools (DE, 2019) dealt with the issue of exemptions as follows:

Pupils may be excluded from standardised testing if, in the view of the school principal, they have a learning or physical disability which would prevent them from attempting the tests or, in the case of migrant students, where the level of

English required in the test would make attempting the test inappropriate. Exemptions should be considered on a case-by-case basis and be warranted only in exceptional cases. Pupils who are deemed not to be in a position to undertake standardised testing should be included in the return of the standardised assessment data to the Department of Education and Skills as “exempt”

A review of assessment for learners with special educational needs conducted for the National Council for Special Education by Douglas et al. (2012) recommended the adoption of the concept of inclusive assessment. This is underpinned by a number of principles.

- Assessment should ensure the measurement of the progress, engagement and outcomes for all learners.
- All students should be included and benefit from assessment and they [assessments] should be accessible and appropriate for the diverse range of students in the education system.

A key recommendation in Douglas et al.’s review was that the National Literacy and Numeracy Strategy should include a commitment to the development of accommodated and alternative approaches to the assessment for children exempted from the norm-referenced standardised tests. These should lead to clear expectations around the consistent assessment and recording of progress including IEP (Individual Educational Programme) goals.

Douglas et al. also recommended that relevant stakeholders should ensure that there are clear expectations of schools regarding consistent assessment and recording of progress of students with SEN across the whole curriculum. They also recommended that the progress of students not included in normed sample-based tests should be communicated to Boards of Management, along with the results of their peers, and that assessment data would be collected from such students as part of national assessments of English reading and mathematics.

A number of large-scale testing programmes have specific arrangements in place so that as many students as possible can participate, and, where students cannot participate, alternative approaches to assessment are available. In England, for example, national curriculum testing includes pre-KS1 (Key Stage 1) and pre-KS2 standards, against which students are assessed if they are studying well below the curriculum for their class level (see below). The most challenged students are assessed using an Engagement Model that focuses on such attributes as exploration, realisation, anticipation, persistence and initiation (see below).

Accommodations are also in place for students who need support to participate in the assessments. These are students with reading difficulties, writing difficulties, concentration difficulties, processing difficulties, a hearing impairment, a visual impairment, or English as an additional language. The accommodations (many of which will be familiar to those working at post-primary level in Ireland, in the context of the state examinations) include

- Additional time
- Adaptations to test papers
- Compensatory marks for spelling
- Scribes
- Transcripts
- Word processors
- Written or oral translators
- Rest breaks
- Prompters
- Accessibility objects in the mathematics test
- Highlighter pens
- Administration of the test in a different location.

The Massachusetts MCAS programme offers an alternative assessment for students with significant cognitive disabilities who are unable to take the standard MCAS tests at Grades 4-8, and Grade 10, even with accommodations. The M-CAS-Alt is intended to enable these students to submit portfolios of their work that demonstrate their performance on curriculum learning standards.⁴

Q6: What Are Some Recent Developments in Reporting on National Large-scale Summative Assessments?

There have been some developments in recent years in the ways in which performance on literacy and numeracy on large-scale assessments has been reported. Some of these developments concern reporting to individual students and their parents, such as reporting of test scores and/or progress scores; others relate to system-level issues, such as measures of school effectiveness. Here, we select a number of current national assessment programmes and discuss their approaches to reporting. It might be noted that, in most cases, the programmes we examine are census-based, with all students at a given grade level taking part

⁴ See <https://www.doe.mass.edu/mcas/alt/default.html>

in the assessment, whether on computer or on paper (see Table 3 for an overview of the assessments).

Australia – NAPLAN

A major national census-based testing programme, the National Assessment Program – Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN), was introduced in 2008 by the Australian government via the Australian Curriculum, Assessment and Reporting Authority (ACARA). Currently, every year all students in Years 3, 5, 7 and 9 are assessed on the same days using national tests in Reading, Writing, Language Conventions (Spelling, Grammar and Punctuation) and Numeracy. Since 2010, NAPLAN results have been published on the Australian Federal Government Website, MySchool (<http://www.myschool.edu.au/>). The purposes of NAPLAN include meeting public accountability, demonstrating transparency, and maintaining public confidence in the standards of schooling (Klenkowski & Wyatt-Smith, 2012). NAPLAN provides comparative data between and within schools over years to allow tracking of student and school development (ACARA, 2015), and these comparative data can be of use to policy makers, school administrators, teachers, and parents. The aims of NAPLAN are supported by incentives for principal teachers to raise test scores, and ‘flying squads’ who support schools that are perceived to be underperforming.

The results for each of the five NAPLAN core assessment domains are reported on a common NAPLAN scale. Rather than a separate scale for each year level tested (3, 5, 7 and 9), the *My School* website shows a single common scale, which purports to show growth over time. The midpoint of each domain scale is set at 500 NAPLAN score points. The mean score varies depending on the year level and test domain, and from test year to test year.

A feature of NAPLAN in recent years has been the gradual introduction of computer-based assessment, with about 50% of students taking NAPLAN online in 2019, an improvement from 15% in 2018 (ACARA, 2021). A full transition to online testing is expected by 2022.

NAPLAN has not been well-received in all quarters. The initiative was strongly criticized by the Australian Primary Principals Association (APPA, 2009) soon after its inception:

These unintended consequences have been identified in terms of: the narrowing of the curriculum as teachers teach only that which is to be tested; curriculum areas that are not tested are neglected; higher order thinking skills that are difficult to assess in such paper and pencil formats are also neglected; time is spent on coaching and practice tests; schools participate in perverse

practices designed to improve achievement data; and finally, as stated in the APPA position paper, ‘a testing industry grows which is driven by its own commercial interests’ (p. 5).

Several other studies have also been critical of NAPLAN. It has been asserted that it fosters an unhelpful competitive culture between schools that results in narrowing of the curriculum (Hardy, 2015; Klenowski & Wyatt-Smith, 2012; Polesel et al., 2014), and has a negative impact on teacher, parent, and student well-being (Dulfer et al., 2012; Polesel et al., 2014; Wyn et al., 2014; Roberts et al., 2019). The assessment of writing in NAPLAN has been criticised for overemphasising spelling, punctuation, grammar and paragraphing at the expense of higher-order writing skills (Pereleman, 2018).

Joseph (2018) has sought to address these and related criticisms. He argues that the ‘failure’ of NAPLAN to improve results over time may arise because schools and teachers do not respond [appropriately] to the results. His argument is that there have been improvements in average scores in some states, but not in others, suggesting differences in policies to raise performance, and their implementation. He also notes that studies of anxiety levels among students and others typically measure anxiety before and after NAPLAN, but do not measure students’ anxiety around other assessments, such as teacher-made tests.

Currently the *My School* website publishes ‘like school’ comparisons of school performance based on the Index of Community Socio-Educational Advantage (ICSEA) scale (see Figures 1 and 2). This scale was developed for the *My School* website to identify schools with similar student populations, with the expectation that individual schools can benchmark their school’s performance or progress against schools (and now students) of similar socio-economic status. Figure 1 shows school-level results in each subject area in a given year, while Figure 2 compares achieved average scores over time, with the average scores of schools of similar socio-economic background.

In addition to the NAPLAN programme, ACARA supports schools with assessment through a project that is currently in development, the Learning Progressions and Online Formative Assessment Initiative (see <https://ofai.edu.au/>). This is intended to support teachers’ assessment of student attainment and growth against clear descriptors, and to assist teachers in monitoring individual student progress and identifying student learning needs through opt-in online and on-demand student learning assessment tools with links to student resources, prioritising early years foundation skills.

Figure 1: Aggregated NAPLAN school results for literacy and numeracy for an individual school (Primary year 3)

Source: <https://www.myschool.edu.au/>

Figure 2: Aggregated NAPLAN school results for reading for an individual school (Primary year 3), compared with other students with a similar background

Source: <https://www.myschool.edu.au/>

England – National Curriculum Key Stage Tests

The National Curriculum Tests (formerly SATS or Standard Assessment Tests) have been a feature of the educational landscape in England since the early 1990s. Pupils are expected to have mastered the skills, knowledge and understanding set out in the national curriculum programmes of study for English and mathematics by the end of key Stages 1 (Year 2, Age 7) and 2 (Year 6, age 11).⁵ In the past, students were awarded levels, based on their performance. Now performance is reported on a scale on which 100 represents the expected standard.⁶ Currently, the tests are compulsory at the end of Key Stages 1 and 2. The tests were abolished for Key Stage 3 (14 year olds) in 2008. Key Stage 1 tests will be made non-statutory (schools will have discretion over whether or not to administer them) from September, 2023.

At the end of KS1 (year 2) pupil attainment is reported through teacher assessment judgements, which are informed by performance on national curriculum tests in mathematics and English reading, as well as teachers' own assessments of students throughout the school year. The tests are administered by teachers in May and marked internally. Each pupil's raw score is converted to a scaled score, with the latter providing an indication of whether a pupil is working at the expected standard. The test results are used in conjunction with evidence from teacher assessment in mathematics, English reading, English writing and science to assess children's knowledge and understanding at the end of the key stage. There is also an optional test of spelling, punctuation and grammar at KS1.

At the end of KS2, all pupils take national curriculum tests in mathematics, English reading, and English grammar, punctuation and spelling. Unlike KS1, the tests are marked externally by trained makers. Students are given a scaled score for each subjects. These achieved scale scores are benchmarked against the students' KS1 scores, providing a measure of progress between the two Key Stages. For example, a student's expected score at KS2 (e.g., in mathematics) is estimated by averaging all KS2 scores nationally for students who achieved the same KS1 score. If a student achieves a scaled score of 110 at KS2, and their expected score (based on KS1 performance) is 105, it means that the student has exceeded the expected score. A school's progress scores (positive and negative) are summed and divided by the number of students involved to generate an overall progress score. Confidence

⁵ Other aspects of England's accountability framework – the Early Years Foundation Stage Profile, the Year 1 Phonics Screening Test, and the Year 4 Multiplication Tables Check are not examined here.

⁶ Reporting of aggregated performance is based on percentages of students achieving the expected standard for their end of Key Stage.

intervals are constructed around school average progress scores to ascertain if they differ from zero progress (Department for Education, 2022).

Schools can order modified versions of the national curriculum tests, including large-print versions and braille versions.

Students with special education needs can be assessed by their teachers on pre-KS1 or pre-KS2 standards, if they are working below the overall standards of the national curriculum tests. The pre-key stage standards focus on key aspects of English reading, English writing and mathematics for the specific purpose of statutory end-of-key stage assessment. The pre-KS standards are not intended to be formative assessment tools to track students throughout a key stage or to guide the individual development of programme (Standards and Testing Agency, 2020a).

An ‘engagement model’ is used to assess students at KS1 and KS2 who are working below the pre-KS1 or pre-KS2 standards. Five areas of engagement are assessed: exploration, realisation, anticipation, persistence and initiation. These areas are intended to enable teachers to assess students’ engagement in developing new skills, knowledge and concepts in the school’s curriculum, as students demonstrate how they achieve specific outcomes. The model is intended to be implemented throughout the school year, enabling both formative and summative assessment. While schools do not have to formally submit students’ scores on the model, they are required to identify those students who are assessed under the model. The engagement model replaces the older P scale (P1-P4) that had been used to assess students with special education needs (Standards and Testing Agency, 2020b).

It is clear that the stakes associated with KS1 assessment in England have been reduced in recent years. There should be less pressure still when they become optional for schools from 2023 onwards. KS2 assessments, which are administered towards the end of post-primary schooling, are still high stakes. An important issue is the extent to which such tests might have negative effects on students’ wellbeing, as well as that of teachers and parents. For example, Bradbury (2019) reported that:

- Primary headteachers in England view Key Stage 2 tests as having a largely negative impact on the staff and pupils in their schools.
- The impact of tests is felt through a range of approaches to preparing for SATs. Many areas of school life are affected, including the curriculum, grouping and intervention

strategies, provision of out-of-hours and holiday revision, and allocation of teachers and teaching assistants.

- Headteachers are concerned about the impact on children: 83% agree that ‘SATs have a negative impact on pupils’ wellbeing’. The main concerns relate to stress and anxiety, and the impact on pupils with SEND⁷ and those seen as ‘vulnerable’.
- Headteachers themselves experience stress and anxiety related to SATs, particularly regarding the possibility of losing their jobs if results go down.
- Many headteachers particularly object to the ways in which SATs results are used in a high stakes system of accountability through their links to Ofsted ratings and the negative comparisons they generate with other schools, as well as their impact on the children.

However, a study by Jerrim (2020) suggests that the average impact of the tests on wellbeing may not be as strong as reported elsewhere. Drawing on data from the Millennium Cohort Study, comparing the wellbeing of pupils in England (measured at around the time they sat the KS2 tests) to students in other parts of the UK (not taking KS2 tests), he found no evidence that the KS2 tests in England were associated with lower levels of happiness, enjoyment of school, self-esteem, or children’s wellbeing. Similarly, no evidence was found that children who are happier, more self-confident or with high levels of wellbeing obtained higher KS2 test scores.

Scotland – Virtual Comparators

Scotland is selected here because it generates performance data on literacy and numeracy based on end-of-schooling performance and facilitates schools in comparing their performance against virtual comparators – students with similar socio-economic characteristics.

Since 2014, for each school leaver in Scotland, ten matching school leavers are randomly selected from a national pool of school leavers, based on gender, additional support needs⁸, stage of leaving school (S4, S5 or S6)⁹ and the social context in which they live,

⁷ Special education needs and disabilities.

⁸ There are three support categories – no additional support needs; additional support needs but student spends at least 80% of their time in mainstream education; additional support needs and student spends less than 80% of their time in mainstream education.

⁹ Fourth, Fifth or Sixth Years (ages 14/15 to 18). Students in S4 complete the National Exams at Levels 3, 4 and 5; those in S5 complete the Highers, and those in S6 the Advanced Highers. Students can enrol in University after completing S5.

based on the Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation.¹⁰ These characteristics are used due to their significance in explaining differences in the attainment and destinations of school leavers in Scotland. Schools can compare their performance to the performance of a Virtual Comparator or pseudo school comprising students from schools in other local authorities who have similar characteristics to the students in the target school. For example, if school X has 20 school leavers, all of whom have the same characteristics, 200 different students with these same characteristics from schools in the other 31 local authorities will be selected for comparison purposes.¹¹ This is intended to enable schools to undertake self-evaluation and improvement activities, by benchmarking their performance against that of the virtual comparator.

A feature of the Scottish system is the inclusion of measures of literacy and numeracy in reporting on performance for school leavers across various levels (school, local education authority, national). Hence, in the case of literacy and numeracy at Secondary level, data are generated on the proportions of students who have achieved SCQF level 4 or better and SCQF level 5 or better, based on the requirements for the Scottish Qualifications Authority's literacy and numeracy units at National 4 and National 5. In some cases, the measures also count unit attainment where a young person has passed all of the units but may not have sat or gained an award in the final examination, e.g. in National 5 Mathematics. Young people will be counted once in this measure, if they have achieved the required level regardless of the number of relevant qualifications they hold.

Figure 3, covering the years 2016 to 2020 for schools under Moray Council (2021) shows the proportions achieving Levels 4 and 5 on Literacy, alongside the corresponding Virtual Comparators. Hence, in 2020, 93% of students achieved Level 4 in literacy in Moray, compared with 94% in the Virtual Comparator, while 81% achieved Level 5, compared with 81% (the same proportion) in the Virtual Comparator.

¹⁰ The Scottish Index of Multiple Deprivation is a relative measure of deprivation across 6,976 small areas (called data zones). If an area is identified as 'deprived', this can relate to people having a low income but it can also mean fewer resources or opportunities. See <https://www.gov.scot/collections/scottish-index-of-multiple-deprivation-2020/>

¹¹ Analyses showed that four matches per target student would have been adequate, but 10 matches are selected to afford greater precision (<https://insight-guides.scotxed.net/technical.htm#Virtual>)

Figure 3: Example of School Report on Literacy Levels, with Corresponding Virtual Comparators

Source: Moray House (2021).

There would seem to be a greater challenge in the area of Numeracy. In 2020, for example, 88% in Moray schools achieved Level 4, compared to 92% in the Virtual Comparator.

Figure 4: Example of School Report on Numeracy Levels, with Corresponding Virtual Comparator

While there has been some discussion on extending Virtual Comparators to primary level in Scotland, concerns have been raised that such elements of literacy as writing, talk and listening would be based on teacher judgements, which might vary across schools (Smith, 2020).

Massachusetts Comprehensive Assessment System (MCAS)

The Massachusetts Comprehensive Assessment System (MCAS) is a standards-based student assessment programme that is implemented annually in Massachusetts at Grades 4-8 and Grade 10¹² in English Language Arts (ELA), Mathematics, and Science and Technology/Engineering (STE). Students with significant learning challenges are administered the MCAS Alternate Assessment (see above). MCAS is currently implementing its ‘second-generation tests’ which include new test designs and item types that are intended to be administered primarily via computer, though the State Department of Education is making paper-based versions available during the transition period and will offer paper-based tests on an ongoing basis as an accommodation for some students.

A key feature of MCAS is the growth model that measures individual student progress by tracking student scores from one year to the next. Students with at least two consecutive years of MCAS scores receive a student growth percentile, which measures how much the student’s performance has changed relative to other students in the state with similar scores in previous years. Growth percentiles range from 1 to 99, with higher numbers indicating higher growth and lower numbers lower growth. In theory, regardless of their MCAS test scores, students have an equal chance to demonstrate growth at any of the 99 percentiles in the following year’s test (Massachusetts State Department of Education, 2019). Growth percentiles are calculated independently of MCAS performance scores/levels. The following are indicative of the types of interpretations that can be made (Massachusetts State Department of Education (2011, p. 2):

- A student with a growth percentile of 90 in 5th grade mathematics grew as much or more than 90 percent of her academic peers (students with similar score histories) from the 4th grade math MCAS to the 5th grade math MCAS. Only 10% of her academic peers grew more in math than she did.
- A student with a growth percentile of 23 in 8th grade English language arts grew as well or better than 23 percent of her academic peers (students with similar score

¹² Some of the assessments are administered in Grade 9, but reported on in Grade 10.

histories) from the 7th grade ELA MCAS to the 8th grade ELA MCAS. This student grew less in ELA than 77% of her academic peers.

In this sense, MCAS student growth percentiles add another layer of understanding, providing a measure of how a student changed from one year to the next relative to other students with similar MCAS test score histories.

Student growth percentiles are also aggregated to understand growth at the subgroup, school, or district level. The most appropriate measure for reporting growth for a group is the median student growth percentile (the middle score if one ranks the individual student growth percentiles from highest to lowest). A typical school or district in the Commonwealth of Massachusetts would have a median student growth percentile of 50. Difference scores from year to year that are less than 10 points are not considered meaningful or significant. Figure 5 shows the individual growth of students at a school. Hovering over a dot in the figure can reveal a student's name (not available here).

Figure 5: MCAS Grade 6 Individual Student Growth by Low Income Status in Grade 6 English Language Arts

Source: Massachusetts State Department of Education (2011), p. 6.

The vertical axis represents student achievement on the grade 6 MCAS ELA test, and the horizontal axis represents student growth from the grade 5 MCAS ELA test to the grade 6 MCAS ELA test. Students shown in the upper right quadrant of the graph demonstrated

higher growth and higher achievement than their peers with similar score histories. Growth can be described as high, moderate or low.

Figure 6 shows a school shows the growth of schools in a school district in English Language Arts (Grade 8). School A is the highest-achieving school, compared with other schools in the district. School B, despite being one of the lowest-achieving schools, has the highest level of student growth. School C has lower achievement than School D, but exhibited marginally greater growth.

Figure 6: Example of MCAS District by Low Income Status in Grade 6 English Language Arts

Source: Massachusetts State Department of Education (2011), p. 7.

The use of percentile growth ranks, especially in the context of teacher evaluation (a purpose for which they have been used in some US states), has been the subject of criticism. For example, Walsh and Isenberg (2015) noted that percentile growth models do not take factors other than prior attainment into account. This can be an issue in disadvantaged contexts, compared to value-added models that take disadvantage into account. Lockwood and Castellano (2014) have suggested alternative approaches to calculating student progress scores. The first is to estimate percentile ranks conditional on past test scores directly, by modelling the conditional cumulative distribution functions, rather than indirectly, through quantile regression. The second is to estimate student growth percentiles directly from longitudinal item-level data, using multi-dimensional item response theory models, rather than from test scale scores, providing an assessment of the bias inherent in student growth

percentile scores. Guarino et al. (2015) have raised concerns about the use of percentile growth models when assignment of students to classes is non-random, arguing instead that value-added models controlled for fixed teacher effects are better.

In 2017, MCAS was ‘re-set’, some 20 years after the original MCAS was introduced. Part of this process involved replacing proficiency levels with achievement levels. The four levels of achievement are:¹³

- *Exceeding expectations* - A student who performed at this level exceeded grade-level expectations by demonstrating mastery of the subject matter.
- *Meeting expectations* - A student who performed at this level met grade-level expectations and is academically on track to succeed in the current grade in this subject.
- *Partially meeting expectations* - A student who performed at this level partially met grade-level expectations in this subject. The school, in consultation with the student's parent/guardian, should consider whether the student needs additional academic assistance to succeed in this subject.
- *Not meeting expectations* - A student who performed at this level did not meet grade-level expectations in this subject. The school, in consultation with the student's parent/guardian, should determine the coordinated academic assistance and/or additional instruction the student needs to succeed in this subject.

Parents of students who are partially meeting expectations or are not meeting expectations are advised to attend family-teacher conferences, and discuss any concerns they may have; to talk to their children about their day in school to reinforce learning; and to communicate to their children that education is important. Parents of children who are partially meeting expectations or are not meeting expectations are advised to have a conversation with their child’s teacher about ways to ensure that their child remains challenged and engaged.

¹³ https://www.doe.mass.edu/odl/e-learning/mcas-parentguide/content/index.html#/list/cj4jyvcuy00003d65dq4633ho?_k=y13ebm

Table 3: Examples of large-scale national/state assessments

	Grades Covered	Subjects Covered	Frequency /Sample	Purpose
Australia National Assessment Programme – Literacy and Numeracy (NAPLAN)	Grades 3, 5, 7 and 9	Literacy (reading and writing) and numeracy; Every three years, science literacy and civics and citizenship education are assessed.	Annually (census)	Monitor system-level quality; monitor progress over time; compare school performance, and implementation of school-level improvement policies.
England Key Stage Tests	Key Stage 1 (Grade 2) and Key Stage 2 (Grade 6)	KS1 – English language, Math KS2 – English language , Math, Science	Annually – all students (census)	Compare school performance, inform stakeholders on individual students’ performance, and school accountability.
Scotland – Scottish Qualifications Authority Senior Phase National Qualifications Results	S4, S5, S6 (final years of schooling)	Literacy, numeracy (extrapolated from assessments of English and mathematics).	Annually	Compare performance of target schools with ‘virtual’ schools – i.e., students with similar SES from other schools
Massachusetts Comprehensive Assessment System (MCAS)	Grades 3-8 and Grade 10 (based on tests taken in Grades 9-10).	English Language Arts, Mathematics (Grades 3-8, 10) and Science Technology/Engineering (Grades 9-10)*	Census-based, annual	Helping schools and districts engage in program evaluation activities, including how well a particular subgroup of students is performing by school and district, across the state. Monitoring the progress of individuals and schools.

Q7: How can 21st century skills related to literacy and numeracy be assessed in large-scale summative assessments?

Since the early 2000's, the term '21st century skills' has been in widespread use. It is intended to capture transversal skills that might not otherwise be taught and assessed in school curricula that are organised by subject matter. In Ireland, some of these skills are evident in the Junior Cycle Framework (DES, 2015), where skills such as being literate, managing myself, staying well, managing information and thinking, being numerate, being creative, working with others, and communicating are identified. Internationally, authors have identified the following as among the most important 21st century skills:

- creativity, critical thinking and problem-solving (Griffin, Care, & McGaw, 2012)
- collaboration and communication (Binkley et al., 2012)
- digital literacy and visual literacy (Greenstein, 2012)
- metacognition (Greenstein, 2012).

While some of these skills seem directly relevant to a revised Literacy, Numeracy and Digital Literacy Strategy (e.g., digital literacy), others, such as critical thinking and (collaborative) problem solving, can also be regarded as important. Indeed, international assessments such as PISA (OECD, 2017) and national assessments such as NAPLAN (ACARA, 2018) have already included assessments of computer-based collaborative problem solving in their testing programmes, often alongside tests of literacy and numeracy. In PISA 2018, a new assessment domain, global competence,¹⁴ was assessed for the first time (OECD, 2020), while PISA assessed aspects of creative thinking in 2022.

However, it might be noted that assessment agencies are still in the early stages of developing assessments of 21st century skills outside the more traditional domains of literacy and numeracy, and it will be some time before a full suite of assessments measuring such skills is available, and their association with literacy, numeracy and other variables have been measured. In the meantime, it is worth examining the extent to which important digital literacy skills are already incorporated into computer-based assessments of literacy and numeracy, such as those offered by PISA, and whether there is a need to incorporate such skills into assessments developed and administered at national level.

¹⁴ The PISA 2018 Global Competence assessment measures students' capacity to examine local, global and intercultural issues, to engage in open, appropriate and effective interactions with people from different cultures, and to act for collective well-being and sustainable development (OECD, 2020)

Many national and state assessments (but not international ones) include an assessment of writing (an important communication skill), including Australia's NAPLAN, England's SATs at Key Stages 1 and 2, the United State's NAEP, and the Massachusetts MCAS. In general, the purpose of such assessments is to improve standards of writing in schools and classrooms. However, writing assessments do not always achieve this goal. According to Hillocks (2002),

- Writing assessments available at the time typically did not align with state standards, and undermined the teaching of writing in schools and classrooms
- Few assessments allowed for the development of a piece of writing over more than one session (i.e., they represent on-demand, single-prompt assessments)
- There were significant disparities between testing rubrics or criteria and the standards they were intended to reflect
- Scoring rubrics were generally vague and the instruction they promoted was of low quality (the assessments contributed to formulaic writing, such as the five-paragraph essay, thereby eliminating the need for critical thought).
- In scoring persuasive writing, several US states highlighted organisation and elaboration of evidence as the main criteria, but their standard for elaboration was purely quantitative (number of supports for a claim), with minimal attention to quality or accuracy. This could communicate to students (and their teachers) that form rather than content is important, and that students need not take responsibility for what they write.
- These flaws in state writing assessment exercised a disproportionately negative influence on writing pedagogy, with, for example, some teachers focusing only on those elements of the writing process likely to be rewarded by scoring rubrics.

To remedy these issues, Hillocks called on states to assess writing using both portfolio assessment (where samples of writing are gathered over time) and on-demand writing tasks. He also highlighted practices that required students to write across the curriculum in subjects other than English. Hillocks suggested that teachers should use writing to help students learn inquiry strategies for discovering, elaborating, and testing ideas in different subject areas – something that is supported today under the disciplinary literacy umbrella.

As noted earlier, the assessment of writing has been criticised in NAPLAN, on the basis that it over-emphasises spelling, punctuation, grammar and paragraphing at the expense of higher-order writing skills (Pereleman, 2018). It has also been acknowledged that progress in

NAPLAN writing has been slower than in other subjects assessed in Australia (Joseph, 2018). The US National Assessment of Educational Achievement (NAEP) last assessed writing at Grades 4 and 8 in 2017, but has yet to release results, as technical issues (differences in the devices used in 2017 and in earlier assessments) resulted in lower performance in 2017 (NAEP, n.d.).

Nevertheless, there would be value in exploring if there is a case to be made to include writing in future national assessments in Ireland, noting that considerable care will need to be exercised in determining which devices should be used by students as they demonstrate their writing skills.

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